

The reach and impact of migration information campaigns in 25 communities across Africa and Asia: technical note

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This document provides technical documentation of the regression analyses reported in the article ‘The reach and impact of migration information campaigns in 25 communities across Africa and Asia’, published in *Migration Policy and Practice* Vol. XII, Number 3, 2024.

Variables used in the analyses

Table 1 presents all variables used in the logistic regressions.

Table 1. Variables used in logistic regressions

Variable name	Variable label
o02ra_c	Research area
c03prefleavecntry_d	Prefers to leave country (next 5 years)
c08wouldleave_d	Would migrate to richer country if given papers
wamexposure_d	Exposed to campaign warning against migrating
wamchannels_n	Number of channels by which the respondent has been exposed to warning against migrating
wamfivechannels_d	Has been exposed to warning against migrating through five channels
grewupra_d	Respondent grew up in research area
livedhi_d	Has lived in high-income country for at least one year
failmig_d	Knows of someone’s failed migration experience
migaware_d	Is aware of current, recent or former international migrant
ffhicont_d	Has family/relatives/friends in a high-income country and has had contact
ffrremit_d	Household has received remittances (past year)
fffreturnhi_d	Has returnee family/relative/friend(s) that lived in high-income country
o20female_d	Is female
a01age_n	Age
a01age2_n	Age squared
edulevel_c4_2	Educational attainment: Incomplete or complete primary
edulevel_c4_3	Educational attainment: Lower or upper secondary
edulevel_c4_4	Educational attainment: Tertiary
workforce_c3_2	Respondent is in the workforce but unemployed
workforce_c3_3	Respondent is not in the workforce
hwira_n	Household Wealth Index
hwira2_n	Household Wealth Index (squared)
cohabitsts_d	Respondent is married/cohabiting (lives in household or elsewhere)

Data source: MIGNEX survey dataset (restricted variant, v1).

Table 2 – Results of pooled dataset analyses (whole sample)

Table 2 presents the results of the pooled dataset logistic regressions. We construct this table of results by running the following syntax in Stata 17:

```
svy: logit depvar1 indepvar2 grewupra_d livedhi_d failmig_d migaware_d
ffhicont_d ffrremit_d fffreturnhi_d o20female_d a01age_n a01age2_n
edulevel_c4_2 edulevel_c4_3 edulevel_c4_4 workforce_c3_2 workforce_c3_3 hwira_n
hwira2_n cohabitsts_d parentyngchild_d i.o02ra_c

margins, dydx(*) atmeans post
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Table 2. Logistic regression of migration aspirations, marginal effects

Independent variables	Prefers to leave country (next 5 years)			Would migrate to richer country if given papers			Prefers to leave and would migrate to richer country if given papers		
Exposed to campaign warning against migrating	0.01 (0.02)			0.00 (0.02)			0.01 (0.02)		
Number of channels by which exposed to warning against migrating		0.01 (0.01)			0.01 (0.01)			0.01 (0.01)	
Has been exposed to warning against migrating through five channels			0.02 (0.04)			-0.02 (0.04)			0.02 (0.04)
Respondent grew up in research area	-0.00 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.00 (0.02)	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	-0.00 (0.02)	-0.00 (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)
Has lived in high-income country for at least one year	0.12** (0.06)	0.12** (0.06)	0.10* (0.06)	0.00 (0.06)	0.00 (0.06)	-0.01 (0.06)	0.11* (0.06)	0.11* (0.06)	0.09 (0.06)
Knows of someone's failed migration experience	0.06*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)
Is aware of current, recent or former international migrant	0.13*** (0.02)	0.13*** (0.02)	0.13*** (0.02)	0.09*** (0.02)	0.09*** (0.02)	0.09*** (0.02)	0.13*** (0.02)	0.13*** (0.02)	0.13*** (0.02)
Has family/relatives/friends in a high-income country and has had contact	0.05*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)
Household has received remittances (past year)	0.04** (0.02)	0.04** (0.02)	0.04** (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)	-0.00 (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)	0.03 (0.02)	0.03 (0.02)	0.03* (0.02)
Has returnee family/relative/friend(s) that lived in high-income country	-0.02 (0.02)	-0.02 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.00 (0.02)	-0.02 (0.02)	-0.02 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.02)
Is female	-0.11*** (0.02)	-0.11*** (0.02)	-0.11*** (0.02)	-0.08*** (0.01)	-0.08*** (0.01)	-0.08*** (0.01)	-0.11*** (0.02)	-0.11*** (0.02)	-0.11*** (0.02)
Age	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)
Age (squared)	-0.00* (0.00)	-0.00* (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)	-0.00* (0.00)	-0.00* (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)
Educational attainment: Incomplete or complete primary	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)
Educational attainment: Lower or upper secondary	0.10*** (0.02)	0.10*** (0.02)	0.10*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.09*** (0.02)	0.09*** (0.02)	0.09*** (0.02)
Educational attainment: Tertiary	0.14*** (0.03)	0.14*** (0.03)	0.14*** (0.03)	0.12*** (0.02)	0.12*** (0.02)	0.12*** (0.02)	0.14*** (0.03)	0.13*** (0.03)	0.13*** (0.03)
Respondent is in the workforce but unemployed	0.07*** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)
Respondent is not in the workforce	0.05*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.04** (0.02)	0.04** (0.02)	0.04** (0.02)
Household Wealth Index	0.00*** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	0.00** (0.00)	0.00** (0.00)	0.00** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)
Household Wealth Index (squared)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (0.00)
Respondent is married/cohabiting (lives in household or elsewhere)	-0.07*** (0.02)	-0.07*** (0.02)	-0.07*** (0.02)	-0.05** (0.02)	-0.04** (0.02)	-0.04** (0.02)	-0.06*** (0.02)	-0.06*** (0.02)	-0.05*** (0.02)
Respondent is parent of at least one child younger than fifteen years old	-0.05*** (0.02)	-0.05*** (0.02)	-0.05*** (0.02)	-0.04*** (0.02)	-0.04*** (0.02)	-0.04*** (0.02)	-0.06*** (0.02)	-0.06*** (0.02)	-0.06*** (0.02)
Observations	11,942	11,942	12,414	12,023	12,023	12,496	11,825	11,825	12,294

Data source: MIGNEX survey dataset (restricted variant, v1). N=12,023. Data are weighted to reflect the survey design. Standard errors in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

¹ Where *depvar* is any of: c03prefleavenentry_d, c08wouldleave_d or c03prefleavenentry_d*c08wouldleave_d

² Where *indepvar* is any of: wamexposure_d, wamchannels_n or wamfivechannels_d

Table 3– Results of research area analyses (context specific analyses)

Table 3 presents the results of the research area logistic regressions. The results are presented in terms of the marginal effects of each independent variable. We construct this table of results by running the following syntax in stata 17:

```
svy: logit depvar3 indepvar4 grewupra_d livedhi_d failmig_d migaware_d
ffhicont_d ffrremit_d fffreturnhi_d o20female_d a01age_n a01age2_n
edulevel_c4_2 edulevel_c4_3 edulevel_c4_4 workforce_c3_2 workforce_c3_3 hwira_n
hwira2_n cohabitsts_d parentyngchild_d if ra=='i'5

margins, dydx(*) atmeans post
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Table 3. Logistic regression of migration aspirations, marginal effects by research area

Dependent variable	Readiness to migrate (Would leave to a richer country if given papers)			Preference to migrate (Would prefer to leave the country during next 5 years)		
Independent variable	Exposed to campaign warning against migrating	Number of channels by which the respondent was exposed to warning against migrating	Exposed to warning against migrating through five channels	Exposed to campaign warning against migrating	Number of channels by which the respondent was exposed to warning against migrating	Exposed to warning against migrating through five channels
Research area						
São Nicolau (CPV1)	-0.01	0.01	-0.08	0.15*	0.06	●
Boa Vista (CPV2)	0.07	0.03	-0.20	0.02	-0.00	-0.40
Boffa (GIN1)	0.05	0.01	0.02	-0.01	-0.03*	-0.18*
Dialakoro (GIN2)	-0.07	-0.01	●	0.12	0.04	●
Gbane (GHA1)	-0.02	0.01	●	-0.13	-0.09**	●
Golf City (GHA2)	-0.08*	-0.03*	-0.11	-0.03	-0.01	-0.25
New Takoradi (GHA3)	0.00	0.00	●	0.05	0.02	0.32**
Down Quarters (NGA1)	0.03	0.03	●	0.01	0.05	●
Awe (NGA2)	0.36*	0.14	●	0.22	0.08	●
Ekpoma (NGA3)	●	●	●	●	●	●
Batu (ETH2)	0.04	0.03*	0.03	-0.01	0.00	-0.08
Moyale (ETH3)	-0.02	0.01	0.01	0.07	0.02	0.09
Erigavo (SOM1)	0.01	0.04	0.38	0.07	0.06**	0.38
Baidoa (SOM2)	-0.19***	-0.06***	-0.39***	-0.32***	-0.06**	-0.27*
Enfidha (TUN1)	0.01	-0.01	-0.07	0.00	-0.01	0.05
Redeyef (TUN2)	0.05	0.03**	-0.06	0.05	0.03	0.29***
Hopa (TUR1)	0.04	-0.04	●	●	●	●
Yenice (TUR2)	●	●	●	●	●	●
Kilis (TUR3)	0.02	0.08	●	-0.03	-0.06	●
Shahrake Jabrael (AFG1)	-0.01	-0.01	●	0.09	0.05**	●
Behsud (AFG2)	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.02	-0.06
Shahrake Mahdia (AFG3)	0.07	0.01	●	0.10*	0.05**	●
Chot Dheeran (PAK1)	●	●	●	●	●	●
Youhanabad (PAK2)	-0.09	0.01	●	-0.17	-0.05	●
Keti Bandar (PAK3)	0.63***	0.50**	●	0.01	0.00	●

Data source: MIGNEX survey dataset (restricted variant, v1). Data are weighted to reflect the survey design. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. ● denotes that the regression was not possible to run as there were too few observations for the dependent or independent variable. Blue colour coded results denote positive statistically significant effects. Red colour coded results denote negative statistically significant effects.

³ Where *depvar* is any of the three dependent variables of interest: c03prefleaveentry_d, c08wouldleave_d or c03prefleaveentry_d*c08wouldleave_d

⁴ Where *indepvar* is any of the three independent variables of interest: wamexposure_d, wamchannels_n or wamfivechannels_d

⁵ Where 'i' denotes the number identifier of any of the 25 research areas from the MIGNEX survey.